

World-class Universities, a Dynamic Multivariate Analysis Through International Rankings

Marcelo Ruiz Toledo

Departamento de Estadísticas, Universidad de Salamanca,
37007 Salamanca, España, mruiz@usal.es
Centro de Investigación Institucional, Universidad Bernardo
O'Higgins, Santiago, Chile.

Claudio Ruff Escobar

Universidad Bernardo O'Higgins, Centro de Investigación
Institucional, Santiago, Chile cruff@ubo.cl

Helena Martín Rodero

Universidad de Salamanca Facultad de Medicina
Departamento de Estadística Alfonso X El Sabio, s/n. 37007
Salamanca, Spain helena@usal.es

María Teresa Gómez Marcos

Departamento de Estadísticas, Universidad de Salamanca,
37007 Salamanca, España

Purificación Galindo Villardón

Departamento de Estadísticas, Universidad de Salamanca,
37007 Salamanca, España pgalindo@usal.es

María Purificación Vicente Galindo

Universidad de Salamanca Facultad de Medicina
Departamento de Estadística Alfonso X El Sabio, s/n. 37007
Salamanca, Spain purivg@usal.es

Abstract — International rankings have achieved great prestige as an instrument for measuring university excellence as a quality assurance mechanism. Thus, this research aims to observe the behavior of the best-positioned universities in these rankings, as well as the trajectories of indicators and institutions. In fact, the Top-15 universities of ARWU, THE, and QS were selected, and an analysis was carried out using the Dynamic Biplot technique, which allows the study of the relationship between a set of multivariate data developed on more than one occasion. The results prove that world-class universities show different characteristics and trajectories when analyzed multivariate and dynamically. The ranking indicators also reveal different correlations that may affect the final ranking.

Keywords - rankings; universities; ARWU Ranking; Times Ranking; QS Ranking

I. INTRODUCCIÓN.

The higher education quality has become a transcendent matter in the last years. To certify this quality, multiple international rankings that aim to do a comprehensive assessment of universities have emerged in parallel to the accreditation system. In fact, international classifications are an assessment tool that facilitates comparing the performance of different academic institutions[1].

International ranking's impact on higher education institutions' governance is increasing, and the rankings are strengthening as common instruments to assess the excellence of university systems [2]. Regarding this framework, stakeholders often use rankings to make different institutional decisions. At the same time, international students, especially those with higher income, use rankings as mechanisms to confirm the center's selection in which they will study. Likewise, each country's government uses rankings to allocate funds for

scholarships, and the universities use them to design their strategic plans[3].

Concerning the previous paragraph, the use of a limited number of indicators, the comparability, and the interpretation facility are some factors that have popularized its implementation in the last years. In this respect, as Pandiella-Dominique [4] and Hazelhorn [5] have proposed, there are two reasons for the ranking phenomenon: first, the higher education internationalization addressed to the talent search. Second, the commodification is oriented towards competition for the prestige that influences the student choice.

Although the ranking phenomenon is a highly topical issue, the emerge of this institution list is not new. One of its precedents is the classification published by Jack Gorman between 1967 and 1983, which intended to list a hundred of North American university programs and others from the rest of the world, considering their quality [6]. Nevertheless, it was in the early 21st century when the international rankings became more important and visible in a great part of the world due to their dissemination through the Internet [7].

Among the more well-known international rankings, it is possible to highlight those centered on the scientific production, which is highly measurable and quantifiable, also those based on certain factors associated with institutional Prestige [8]. Concerning this, Parelleda and Álvarez [9] consider that the highest impact lists are precisely those that simplify the most of their results. In other words, they present a classification table and a general score that can be easily intelligible. Thus, the three classifications that better meet those criteria are Academic Ranking of World Universities (ARWU), Times Higher Education World University Rankings (THE), and QS World University Rankings (QS).

- [23] Trigwell K (2011) Measuring teaching performance. In: Shin JC, Toutkoushian RK (eds) *University Rankings. Theoretical basis, methodology and global higher education impacts on* . Springer Netherlands, London, pp 165–181
- [24] Aguillo IF, Bar-Ilan J, Levene M, Ortega JL (2010) Comparing university rankings. *Scientometrics* 85:243–256. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-010-0190-z>
- [25] Luque-Martínez T, Faraoni N, Doña-Toledo L (2018) Meta-ranking de universidades. Posicionamiento de las universidades Españolas. *Rev Esp Doc Cient* 41:e198–e198. <https://doi.org/10.3989/redc.2018.1.1456>
- [26] Docampo D, Cram L (2015) On the effects of institutional size in university classifications: the case of the Shanghai ranking. *Scientometrics* 1325–1346. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-014-1488-z>
- [27] Uslu B (2020) A path for ranking success: what does the expanded indicator-set of international university rankings suggest? *High Educ* 80:949–972. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-020-00527-0>
- [28] Soh K (2015) What the Overall doesn't tell about world university rankings: examples from ARWU, QSWUR, and THEWUR in 2013. *J High Educ Policy Manag* 37:295–307. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1360080X.2015.1035523>
- [29] Shehatta I, Mahmood K (2016) Correlation among top 100 universities in the major six global rankings: policy implications. *Scientometrics* 109:1231–1254. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-016-2065-4>
- [30] Hou YW, Jacob WJ (2017) What contributes more to the ranking of higher education institutions? A comparison of three world university rankings. *Int Educ J* 16:29–46
- [31] Tuesta EF, Garcia-Zorita C, Ayllon RR, Sanz-Casado E (2019) Does a Country/Region's Economic Status Affect Its Universities' Presence in International Rankings? *J Data Inf Sci* 4:56–78. <https://doi.org/10.2478/jdis-2019-0009>
- [32] Liu Z, Moshi GJ, Awuor CM (2019) Sustainability and indicators of newly formed world-class universities (NFWCUs) between 2010 and 2018: Empirical analysis from the rankings of ARWU, QSWUR and THEWUR. *Sustain* 11:2745. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11102745>
- [33] Jeremic V, Bulajic M, Martic M, Radojicic Z (2011) A fresh approach to evaluating the academic ranking of world universities. *Scientometrics* 87:587–596. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-011-0361-6>
- [34] Fermín J, Miguélez E (2015) BIPILOT DINÁMICO. USAL
- [35] Galindo P (1986) Una alternativa de representación simultánea: HJ-Biplot. Salamanca
- [36] Docampo D (2008) International rankings and quality of the university systems. *Rev Educ* 1:149–176
- [37] Soh K (2021) Don't Read University Rankings Like Reading Football League Tables: Taking a Close Look at the Indicators. *World Univ Rank* 1–17